

A checklist of the spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Lowveld National Botanical Garden, South Africa

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ABSTRACT: An annotated species list of spiders presently known from the Lowveld National Botanical Garden in Mpumalanga, South Africa, is provided. A total of 146 species from 35 families and 110 genera are currently protected in the garden. The most species-rich families are Araneidae (24 species), Thomisidae (21 species), and Salticidae (14 species), while singletons are represented by 13 families. The global distribution, endemism, and conservation status for each species are provided, and species of special concern are identified, as well as possible new species. Most of the species (97.9%) have a wide distribution range and are of Least Concern, only one species is listed as Rare, and two species might be new to science. Only one species is endemic to the Lowveld, and 37 are Mpumalanga endemics.

Keywords: South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa), conservation, endemism,

INTRODUCTION

In this paper, we look at the spider diversity of the Lowveld National Botanical Garden (LNBG) in Mpumalanga, South Africa. The garden was established in 1969 to promote, conserve, and display the wealth and diversity of the Flora of river landscapes and the rich plant diversity of the Lowveld (Willis & Morkel, 2007).

The formation of the South African National Biodiversity Institute (SANBI) in September 2004, through the proclamation of the National Environmental Management: Biodiversity Act (NEMBA), provided an ideal opportunity to showcase the biological diversity held within South Africa's national botanical gardens. There are inevitably many gaps in our knowledge and understanding of the faunal diversity conserved in our gardens. The Administrator of the Transvaal officially opened the Garden on 10 September 1971. A portion of the 165 ha it occupies was donated by the local municipality, and the rest by the Board of Hall & Sons.

As part of the South African National Survey (SANSa), we have sampled some of the 11 national botanical gardens (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2015). Checklists are already available for the Kirstenbosch National Botanical Garden in the Western Cape (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2023) and the Pretoria National Botanical Garden (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2024). The Free State National Botanical Garden in Bloemfontein was sampled by the staff and students at the University of the Free State and National Museum in Bloemfontein (Butler & Haddad, 2011; Neethling & Haddad, 2013). Presently, surveys are underway in the Walter Sisulu National Botanical Garden (Leroy & Leroy, 2025).

STUDY AREA

The Lowveld National Botanical Garden (25°26'40"S 30°57'58"E) is a subtropical garden located just outside Mbombela (formerly Nelspruit) in Mpumalanga, South Africa (Figs 1 & 3). It covers about 165 hectares at the confluence of the Crocodile and Nels Rivers that create spectacular waterfalls and gorges. It has a rich plant diversity with over 600 naturally occurring plant species and around 2,000 introduced species, including indigenous and exotic African plants. Notable flora includes clivias, fig trees, and baobabs along rainforest trails. Of the 165 ha, only 30 ha is cultivated or landscaped, while the remainder are natural or low-maintenance areas. The landscape features a rainforest and an artificial forest walkway. The suspended bridge, which runs from the African Rain Forest, takes visitors 4 m up into the Rain Forest's canopy, providing a bird's-eye view of the Garden's tropical area (Fig. 2).

Figures 1–2. Lowveld National Botanical Garden. 1. Entrance. 2. Suspended bridge in the canopy of the Rain Forest. Credit: Nita Lou Leroux.

Figure 3. The Lowveld National Botanical Garden in Mpumalanga

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Collecting methods, identification, and voucher specimens:

Spiders were sampled during several visits to the garden by members of the Spider Club of Southern Africa and visiting scientists. The following sampling methods were used: pitfall traps, sweeping, and active searching (Figs 4-7). The first author identified the collected specimens, and the voucher specimens are housed in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) in Pretoria. On iNaturalist, from 52 photographs of spiders of the LN BG 14 species were recognized and marked with an asterisk in the checklist (Table 3).

Endemicity value: The endemicity values for each species are provided in Table 2 based on their currently known distribution and seven recognized endemicity categories:

- 6—species are only known from the type locality (LN BG).
- 5—species known only from the Mpumalanga Province (ME).
- 4—species are known from the Mpumalanga Province and an adjoining province.
- 3—known from >three provinces, a South African endemic (SAE).
- 2—known from other countries in Southern Africa (STHE).
- 1—known from several countries in the Afrotropical Region (AE).
- 0—also from outside the Afrotropical Region.

Conservation status: As part of the Red Listing Spider Project (Foord *et al.*, 2020), the preliminary conservation status of species was determined. Immatures, new species, and undetermined taxa were not evaluated (NE). Species known from only one sex, or where only very old material is available, or species that could not be identified were listed as DD (data deficient). Species with a broad distribution (categories 0–2) were of least concern (LC); those of categories 3 and 4 were supposed to be South African endemics (SAE), and many of them are also LC, while species of special concern usually belong to categories 5 or 6.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Numbers present: Not many surveys have been undertaken in Mpumalanga so far, and most have focused on agroecosystems such as avocado, citrus, and macadamia (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2013). A total of 146 species from 35 families and 110 genera are currently protected in the garden (Tables 1 & 3). Data from LN BG compared well with the Pretoria National Botanical Garden, where 152 species from 36 families and 113 genera were sampled (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2024).

Family diversity: Of the 35 spider families collected from LN BG (Tables 1-3) the most species-rich families are Araneidae (24 species), Thomisidae (21 species), and Salticidae (14 species), while singletons are represented by 13 families (Table 3). A photo gallery of some of the spiders sampled at the LN BG is provided (Figs 8–29).

Figures 4–7. Collecting spiders in the Lowveld National Botanical Garden. 4. Type of pitfall trap used. 5. Nita Lou Leroux with pitfall traps. 6. Jurie Kasselman emptying a pitfall trap. 7. John Leroy visual search and hand collecting. Credit: Astri Leroy.

TABLE 1: Spider diversity of the Lowveld National Botanical Garden with the total number of families, genera (G) and species (SPP.)

FAMILIES	GEN	SPP.	FAMILIES	GEN	SPP.
Agelenidae	1	2	Oxyopidae	3	6
Araneidae	17	24	Philodromidae	1	2
Barychelidae	1	1	Pholcidae	2	3
Caponiidae	1	1	Phyxelididae	1	1
Cheiracanthiidae	2	3	Pisauridae	3	4
Clubionidae	1	3	Salticidae	11	14
Corinnidae	4	4	Scytodidae	1	1
Ctenidae	2	2	Segestriidae	1	1
Deinopidae	1	1	Selenopidae	1	2
Eresidae	1	1	Sparassidae	3	4
Gallieniellidae	1	1	Tetragnathidae	2	5
Gnaphosidae	6	6	Theridiidae	7	9
Hersiliidae	1	1	Thomisidae	14	21
Linyphiidae	2	2	Trachelidae	1	1
Liocranidae	1	1	Trochanteriidae	1	1
Lycosidae	8	9	Uloboridae	4	4
Mimetidae	2	2	Zodariidae	1	1
Oecobiidae	2	2		110	146

TABLE 2: Conservation status and endemism of the spider species sampled at the Lowveld National Botanical Garden .

CONSERVATION STATUS	NO. SPP.	%
Not evaluated NE	2	1.4
Data deficient DD	0	0
Least concern LC	143	97.9
Rare	1	0.7
ENDEMICITY		
0 – Africa and wider (C)	20	13.7
1 – African endemics (AE)	77	52.7
2 – Southern African endemics (STHE)	23	15.8
3 – South African endemics (SAE)	25	17.1
4 – South African endemics (SAE): two adjacent provinces	0	0
5 – Mpumalanga endemics (ME)	1	0.7
6 – Type locality	0	0

Endemism: Twenty species (13.7%) sampled at LNBG have a distribution wider than Africa, while 77 species (52.7%) are African endemics (AE), 25 species (17%) are Southern African endemics, and 26 species (17.8%) are South African endemics (Table 2). Only one species *Austrachelas bergi* Haddad, Lyle, Bosselaers & Ramirez, 2009 is a Limpopo endemic.

Conservation status: One Agelenidae species and one Uloboridae species are possibly new and were not evaluated. *Quamtana embuleni* Huber, 2003 has a small range (< 20 000 km²) hence it is regarded as rare. The remaining 143 (97.9%) species have a wide distribution, are not known to face threats, and are listed as Least Concern.

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Figures 8–29. Spiders from the Lowveld National Botanical Garden. 8. *Araneus apricus* (Vicky Field). 8. *Eriovixia excelsa* (Vicky Field). 10. *Singa albodorsata* (Vicky Field). 11. *Trichonephila fenestrata* (Paul Hoekman). 12. *Gasteracantha versicolor* (Natti Strydom). 13. *Messapus natalis* (Christofer Willis). 14. *Asiainopis anchietae* (Aart Louw). 15. *Scytodes maritima* (Robert Wienand). 16. *Vicirionessa mustela* (Vicky Field). 17. *Nilus curtus* (Peter Webb). 18. *Nilus margaritatus* (Rob Palmer). 19. *Ctenus gulosus* (Peter Webb). 20. *Foveosa foveolata* (Peter Webb). 21. *Thyene natalii* (Vicky Field). 22. *Oxyopes bothai* (Peter Webb). 23. *Vicirionessa mustela* (Vicky Field). 24. *Helaffricanus insperatus* (Vicky Field). 25. *Miagrammopes brevicauda* (Peter Webb). 26. *Runcinia aethiops* (Vicky Field). 27. *Thomisus scrupeus* (Peter Webb). 28. *Tmarus comellini* (Peter Webb). 29. *Monaeses pustulosus* (Martie Rheeder).

TABLE 3: Spiders of Lowveld National Botanical Garden listing their endemcity (END), conservation status (CON), country endemcity (CEN) LC Least Concern, Rare, NE Not Evaluated. * Species from iNaturalist.

SPECIES	END	CON	CEN
AGELENIDAE			
<i>Benoitia ocellata</i> (Pocock, 1900)	1	LC	AE
<i>Benoitia</i> sp. 4		NE	
ARANEIDAE			
<i>Arachnura scorpionoides</i> Vinson, 1863	1	LC	AE
<i>Araneus apricus</i> (Karsch, 1884)	1	LC	AE
<i>Argiope australis</i> (Walckenaer, 1805)	1	LC	AE
<i>Argiope flavipalpis</i> (Lucas, 1858)	1	LC	AE
<i>Cyclosa insulana</i> (Costa, 1834)	0	LC	C
<i>Cyclosa oculata</i> (Walckenaer, 1802)	0	LC	C
<i>Cyphalonotus larvatus</i> (Simon, 1881)	1	LC	AE
<i>Cyrtophora citricola</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	0	LC	C
<i>Eriovixia excelsa</i> (Simon, 1889)	0	LC	C
<i>Gasteracantha milvoides</i> Butler, 1873 *	1	LC	AE
<i>Gasteracantha versicolor</i> (Walckenaer, 1841) *	1	LC	AE
<i>Gea infusata</i> Tullgren, 1910	1	LC	AE
<i>Isoxya stuhlmanni</i> Bosenberg & Lenz, 1895	1	LC	AE
<i>Nemoscolus cotti</i> Lessert, 1933	2	LC	STHE
<i>Neoscona blondeli</i> (Simon, 1886)	1	LC	AE
<i>Neoscona rufipalpis</i> (Lucas, 1858)	1	LC	AE
<i>Neoscona subfusca</i> (C.L. Koch, 1837)	0	LC	C
<i>Neoscona triangula</i> (Keyserling, 1864)	0	LC	C
<i>Paraplectana thornstoni</i> (Blackwall, 1865)	1	LC	AE
<i>Pararaneus cyrtoscapus</i> (Pocock, 1898)	1	LC	AE
<i>Prasonica seriata</i> Simon, 1895	1	LC	AE
<i>Singa albidorsata</i> Kauri, 1950 *	3	LC	SAE
<i>Trichonephila fenestrata</i> (Thorell, 1859) *	2	LC	STHE
<i>Trichonephila senegalensis annulata</i> (Thorell, 1859)	2	LC	STHE
BARYCHELIDAE			
<i>Pisenor arcturus</i> (Tucker, 1917)	2	LC	STHE
CAPONIIDAE			
<i>Caponia spirifer</i> Purcell, 1904	3	LC	SAE
CHEIRACANTHIIDAE			
<i>Cheiracanthium africanum</i> Lessert, 1921	1	LC	AE
<i>Cheiracanthium furculatum</i> Karsch, 1879	1	LC	AE
<i>Cheiramiona krugerensis</i> Lotz, 2003	3	LC	SAE
CLUBIONIDAE			
<i>Clubiona abbajensis</i> Strand, 1906	1	LC	AE
<i>Clubiona africana</i> Lessert, 1921	1	LC	AE
<i>Clubiona pupillar</i> Lawrence, 1938	3	LC	SAE
CORINNIDAE			
<i>Cambalida dippenaarae</i> Haddad, 2012	1	LC	AE
<i>Copa flavoplumosa</i> Simon, 1886	1	LC	AE
<i>Copuetta lacustris</i> (Strand, 1916)	1	LC	AE
<i>Messapus natalis</i> (Pocock, 1898)	2	LC	STHE
CTENIDAE			
<i>Ctenus gulosus</i> Des Arts, 1912	2	LC	STHE
<i>Ctenus transvaalensis</i> Benoit, 1981	3	LC	SAE

SPECIES	END	CON	CEN
DEINOPIIDAE			
<i>Asianopis anchietae</i> (Brito Capello, 1867)	1	LC	AE
ERESIDAE			
<i>Dresserus colsoni</i> Tucker, 1920	3	LC	SAE
GALLIENIELIDAE			
<i>Austrachelas bergi</i> Haddad, Lyle, Bosselaers & Ramirez, 2009	5	LC	SAE
GNAPHOSIDAE			
<i>Aphantaulex inornata</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE
<i>Asemesthes paynteri</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE
<i>Haplodrassodes splendens</i> (Tucker, 1923)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Xerophaeus bicavus</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE
<i>Zelotes natalensis</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE
<i>Zelotes uquathus</i> FitzPatrick, 2007	3	LC	SAE
HERSILIIDAE			
<i>Hersilia sericea</i> Pocock, 1898	1	LC	AE
LINYPHIIDAE			
<i>Microlinyphia sterilis</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE
<i>Ostearius melanopygius</i> (O.P.-Cambridge, 1880)	0	LC	C
LIOCRANIDAE			
<i>Rhaeboctesis trinotatus</i> Tucker, 1920	2	LC	STHE
LYCOSIDAE			
<i>Allocosa aurata</i> (Purcell, 1903)	3	LC	SAE
<i>Allocosa tuberculipalpa</i> (Caporiacco, 1940)	1	LC	AE
<i>Foveosa foveolata</i> (Purcell, 1903)	1	LC	AE
<i>Hippasa australis</i> Lawrence, 1927	1	LC	AE
<i>Hogna transvaalica</i> (Simon, 1898)	3	LC	SAE
<i>Pirata africana</i> (Roewer, 1960)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Proevippa bruneipes</i> (Purcell, 1903)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Spiniculosa crassipalpis</i> (Purcell, 1903)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Wadicosa manubriata</i> (Simon, 1898)	1	LC	AE
MIMETIDAE			
<i>Anansi natalensis</i> (Lawrence, 1938)	3	LC	SAE
<i>Ero capensis</i> Simon, 1895	2	LC	STHE
OECOBIIDAE			
<i>Oecobius navus</i> Blackwall, 1859	0	LC	C
<i>Uroecobius ecribellatus</i> Kullmann & Zimmermann, 1976	3	LC	SAE
OXYOPIIDAE			
<i>Hamataliwa kulczynskii</i> (Lessert, 1915)	1	LC	AE
<i>Oxyopes bothai</i> Lessert, 1915	1	LC	AE
<i>Oxyopes flavipalpis</i> (Lucas, 1858)	1	LC	AE
<i>Oxyopes schenkeli</i> Lessert, 1927	1	LC	AE
<i>Oxyopes vogelsangeri</i> Lessert, 1946	1	LC	AE
<i>Peuceetia striata</i> Karsch, 1878	1	LC	AE
PHILODROMIDAE			
<i>Philodromus brachycephalus</i> Lawrence, 1952	1	LC	AE
<i>Philodromus guineensis</i> Millot, 1942	1	LC	AE

SPECIES	END	CON	CEN
PHOLCIDAE			
<i>Quamtana bonamanzi</i> Huber, 2003	3	LC	SAE
<i>Quamtana embuleni</i> Huber, 2003	3	Rare	SAE
<i>Smeringopus natalensis</i> Lawrence, 1947	1	LC	AE
PHYXELIIDAE			
<i>Xevioso orthomeles</i> Griswold, 1990	2	LC	STHE
PISAURIDAE			
<i>Nilus curtus</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1876 *	1	LC	AE
<i>Nilus margaritatus</i> (Pocock, 1898)	1	LC	AE
<i>Perenethis simoni</i> (Lessert, 1916)	1	LC	AE
<i>Rothus aethiopicus</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE
SALTICIDAE			
<i>Asemona clara</i> Wesolowska & Haddad, 2013	2	LC	SAE
<i>Baryphas ahenus</i> Simon, 1902	1	LC	AE
<i>Evarcha prosimilis</i> Wesolowska & Cumming, 2008	1	LC	AE
<i>Hasarius adansoni</i> (Audouin, 1826) *	0	LC	C
<i>Helafricanus debilis</i> (Simon, 1901)	1	LC	AE
<i>Helafricanus insperatus</i> (Wesolowska, 1986) *	1	LC	AE
<i>Hyllus argyrotoxis</i> Simon, 1902*	1	LC	AE
<i>Meleon kenti</i> (Lessert, 1925) *	1	LC	AE
<i>Myrmarachne marshalli</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	1	LC	AE
<i>Pignus simoni</i> (Peckham & Peckham, 1903)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Portia schultzi</i> Karsch, 1878	1	LC	AE
<i>Thyene coccineovittata</i> (Simon, 1886) *	1	LC	AE
<i>Thyene natalii</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	1	LC	AE
<i>Vicirionessa mustela</i> (Simon, 1902)*	2	LC	STHE
SCYTODIDAE			
<i>Scytodes maritima</i> Lawrence, 1938*	3	LC	SAE
SEGESTRIIDAE			
<i>Ariadna corticola</i> Lawrence, 1952*	3	LC	SAE
SELENOPIIDAE			
<i>Anyphops barbertonensis</i> (Lawrence, 1940)	1	LC	AE
<i>Anyphops fitzsimonsi</i> (Lawrence, 1940)	3	LC	SAE
SPARASSIDAE			
<i>Olios chelififer</i> Lawrence, 1937	3	LC	SAE
<i>Olios correvoni nigrifrons</i> Lawrence, 1928	1	LC	AE
<i>Palystes superciliosus</i> L. Koch, 1875	2	LC	STHE
<i>Pseudomicrommata longipes</i> (Bösenberg & Lenz, 1895)	1	LC	AE
TETRAGNATHIDAE			
<i>Leucauge decorata</i> (Blackwall, 1864)	0	LC	C
<i>Leucauge festiva</i> (Blackwall, 1866)	1	LC	AE
<i>Leucauge medjensis</i> Lessert, 1930	1	LC	AE
<i>Tetragnatha subsquamata</i> Okuma, 1985	1	LC	AE
<i>Tetragnatha vermiformis</i> Emerton, 1884	0	LC	C
THERIDIIDAE			
<i>Anelosimus nelsoni</i> Agnarsson, 2006	3	LC	SAE
<i>Argyrodes convivans</i> Lawrence, 1937	2	LC	STHE
<i>Enoplognatha molesta</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1904	3	LC	SAE

SPECIES	END	CON	CEN
<i>Latrodectus geometricus</i> C.L. Koch, 1841	0	LC	C
<i>Phoroncidia eburnea</i> (Simon, 1895)	3	LC	SAE
<i>Steatoda capensis</i> Hann, 1990	0	LC	C
<i>Steatoda capensis</i> Hann, 1990	0	LC	C
<i>Theridion pictum</i> (Walckenaer, 1802)*	0	LC	C
<i>Tidarren cuneolatum</i> (Tullgren, 1910)	1	LC	AE
THOMISIDAE			
<i>Ansiea tuckeri</i> (Lessert, 1919)	1	LC	AE
<i>Diaea puncta</i> Karsch, 1884	1	LC	AE
<i>Firmicus bragantinus</i> (Brito Capello, 1866)	1	LC	AE
<i>Heriaeus crassispinus</i> Lawrence, 1942	1	LC	AE
<i>Misumenops rubrodecoratus</i> Millot, 1942	1	LC	AE
<i>Monaeses pustulosus</i> Pavesi, 1895	1	LC	AE
<i>Oxytate argenteooculata</i> (Strand 1886)	1	LC	AE
<i>Runcinia aethiops</i> (Simon, 1901)	1	LC	AE
<i>Runcinia depressa</i> Simon, 1906	1	LC	AE
<i>Runcinia flavida</i> (Simon, 1881)	0	LC	C
<i>Runcinia grammica</i> (C.L. Koch, 1937)	0	LC	C
<i>Simorcus cotti</i> Lessert, 1936	1	LC	AE
<i>Synema imitatrix</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE
<i>Synema langheldi</i> Dahl, 1907 *	1	LC	AE
<i>Thomisops pupa</i> Karsch, 1879	1	LC	AE
<i>Thomisus daradioides</i> Simon, 1890 *	0	LC	C
<i>Thomisus granulatus</i> Karsch, 1880	1	LC	AE
<i>Thomisus scrupeus</i> (Simon, 1886)	1	LC	AE
<i>Thomisus stenningi</i> Pocock, 1900	1	LC	AE
<i>Tmarus comelinii</i> Garcia-Neto, 1989	1	LC	AE
<i>Xysticus mulleri</i> Lawrence, 1952	2	LC	STHE
TRACHELIDAE			
<i>Afroseto martini</i> (Simon, 1897)	2	LC	STHE
TROCHANTERIIDAE			
<i>Platyoides walteri</i> (Karsch, 1887)	1	LC	AE
ULOBORIDAE			
<i>Miagrammopes brevicaudus</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1882	2	LC	STHE
<i>Philoponella</i> sp.		NE	
<i>Uloborus plumipes</i> Lucas, 1846	0	LC	C
<i>Zosis geniculata</i> (Olivier, 1789)	1	LC	C
ZODARIIDAE			
<i>Cydrela spinimana</i> Pocock, 1898	3	LC	SAE